

An Alternate Fault-Detection Method using Predictive Sensitivity

Larry V. Kirkland OO-ALC/TISA
Dr. Lloyd G. Allred OO-ALC/TISA
Jere D. Wiederholt OO-ALC/TISA
United States Air Force

ABSTRACT

Traditional algorithms for determining defective components using circuit card data can provide inconsistent results. Model-based tools and Expert Systems derive conclusions using circuit performance data, circuit theory and statistics. We have developed a Predictive Sensitivity approach which views failure paths and actual failure data to identify alternate fault-isolation strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional AI systems often tend to hone in on a problem too quickly and don't inter-relate analytically. While probabilistic assessments can be made using small amounts of information, the actual defective failure may have been assigned a low probability or even discarded using the sequential reasoning processes of the more traditional AI approaches. It is often more appropriate to run another test than to jump to a (premature) conclusion. This paper provides a strategy for further testing and alternative fault evaluation.

PROBLEM

Sequential reasoning processes such as fault trees can produce *blind spots* for faults which cannot be isolated using the AI tool—even though the fault may exist in the data available to the AI reasoner. These fault-isolation voids become a hard reality after the technician has replaced the components identified by some AI programs, only to discover that the problem still exists. The process becomes hopeless, as repeated consultation to the AI tool produces the recommendation to continue to replace the same component. What is needed is *alternative methods* to inter-relate failures and provide an indication of other likely components which could be defective.

Predictive Sensitivity is a method whereby suspected defective parts can be cross referenced via the test sequence to other parts which theoretically should be good. Identifying defective parts at any point during testing can be cross-related to tests based on component failure probabilities. The cross-related tests with their associated number of failures can then be analyzed to determine other possible defective parts with their associated probability of failure. Traditional ATE does not usually consider these cross relationships when a unit under test can not be repaired using typical AI or ATE call-outs. Even the repair *experts* may not recognize these cross relationships. These critical cross-relationships are not typically used. Fault diagnosis resorts to trial and error. Some units can sit on the shelf for long periods of time awaiting repair. This paper discusses the algorithm and quantification for predictive sensitivity with the various inter relationships.

ALTERNATIVES

Alternative testing and verification schemes are approached using a "Predictive Sensitivity" factor in the "IDENTIFY DEFECTIVE PARTS at 'ANY POINT DURING TESTING'" menu (Refer to Figure 1).

Figure 1. Predictive Sensitivity Interface.

As Predictive Sensitivity approaches 1, an equilibrium is achieved which causes a directional shift in human logic. When Predictive Sensitivity is 1 or greater, there is a likelihood that more information about a specific failing part can be found in alternative testing. Failure to perform these alternative tests can result in a significant risk of making an erroneous decision.

Inter-relating factors from intelligent modules is a logical orientation of information usage. The logical sequence is as follows:

- Select the 'TEST SELECTION' module.
- Select the 'EXECUTE PROBABLE TESTS TO FAIL based on, "SUSPECTED COMPONENTS"'.
 - Identify the component with the high predictive sensitivity factor.
 - The intelligent system will then display all tests which have tested the suspected defective part.
 - Select the 'PREDICTIVE DIAGNOSTICS' menu.
 - Select the 'IDENTIFY DEFECTIVE PARTS, based on "TESTING RESULTS"'.
 - Identify the tests previously displayed for the suspected defective part.
 - The intelligent system will then display a list of parts which cross-relate to the initial part and therefore can be suspected of being defective.

Figure 2. Testing Strategy Interface.

The information displayed at various points during the selection scheme can be used at any time to aid in the determination of actual defective parts. (See Figure 3). It is also clear that many possibilities exist which can be cross-related. One important aspect is that the intelligent system must have the ability to perform various algorithmic functions to produce all the information needed for cross-relationships.

Figure 3. Fault Identification Interface.

PREDICTIVE SENSITIVITY

Predictive Sensitivity is a ratio of overall test failures to specific test failures for a particular part to produce an indication of cross-relationships that could occur.

The Predictive Sensitivity ratio is associated with each suspect part.

$$PS_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N F_j - F_i}{F_i}$$

where PS = Predictive Sensitivity

F_j = The number of historical failed tests for which the part was defective

Upon examining this ratio, it is clearly evident that when Predictive Sensitivity is high, there are a host of alternative tests which should be consulted before deciding that the suspect part is *the* failed part. The ratio quantifies the overall relationship between alternative tests for a particular part. Other tests can then be executed to see whether or not they fail. If a preponderance of tests fail that are associated with a particular part then there is an extreme likelihood the part is defective.

Another key issue here is that the information derived from executing other tests can be used to further fault-isolate should the suspected defective part prove not to be defective. These critical cross-relationships provide a schema whereby perception becomes ominous and flirtation can exist between human logic and the intelligent software.

INTUITION/JUDGEMENT

Modern physics indicates that every process in the Universe is governed by Chaos as it evolves through time. Chaos is often erratic and ever changing. Testing approaches which do not allow alternative testing schemes so potential avenues can be presented and explored are incomplete and thus tend to leave the operator hanging on

their own personal intuition to either reach a premature conclusion or decide on alternative testing directions.

Human intuition and judgement is dependent on several factors. Excluding the personal talents that exists in particular humans these factors include:

- Inherent variability of human performance.
- Bias.
- Political Ramifications.
- Residual erroneous actions.

Human judgement often consists of a "best guess" based on the person's implicit model of operational behavior. Life may have originated near a critical phase transition, and life naturally survives on the edge of chaos[2]. Experience with control systems teaches us that optimal control is achieved at the threshold of chaos. In traditional control, control factors are substantially reduced to avoid instabilities. The resulting control system is less than optimal. Parallel problems can occur when allowing human control and intervention. Human intuition can consequently be affected either by the inherent variability of human performance, inadequate or non-applicable information analysis, bias, and residual erroneous actions which can not be eliminated[3]. Our approach is to give the human cross relationships so assistance can come in the form of proper data crunching and display.

Human are prone to consider events sequentially, to focus too early on a specific solution, to simplify (or even disregard) temporal variations, and to be overly confident in their own ability to handle a situation. The most efficient strategy is to redesign the environment and, when possible, reduce the need for human problem solving. Guidance should come from cognitive systems and cognitive task analysis routines. The algorithms shown by this paper should be included in machine intelligent packages which provide guidance for the repair process.

The ideal situation is to eliminate the human translation bottleneck that occurs as humans think about machines. The ideal system is one in which a machine is able to communicate in a machine vocabulary in a common machine-based universe[4].

INTELLIGENT SYSTEMS

Intelligent systems should derive cross-relationships using perceived information. The relationships derived should not be limited to nor counter-construed to have specific functions but rather they should be generic and somewhat opaque. All too often, a specific set of criteria for evaluation seems to be the premise whereby AI is integrated into various disciplines. While AI provides the ability of assigning probable outcomes with a limited information base, this capability should not be abused. In the long term, this will prove to be counter-productive since the AI system itself tends to be sequential and predictive, without an open-ended relative evaluation of the

applicable area of use and the information available. If we continue to close our minds and control the thought processes for a specific discipline then we will never advance AI systems past their infancy stage. Marvin Minsky stated that we should build true intelligent systems[1] and put them to use.

SENSOR-BASED ALGORITHMS

Algorithms for the predictive sensitivity factor are applicable to a wide range of test/diagnosis routines. The operator can use them for direct testing flow and to construct a UUT fault-isolation sequence which is truly dynamic. The dynamic function relates to having a kind of internal understanding of the UUT, similar to what humans have with each other.

CONCLUSION

As we have shown, the exercising of erroneous logic is not restricted to humans. Machine intelligent algorithms can be victimized by the similar lack of foresight. Peculiar characteristics are not only applicable to humans but also to all machines. Machines however tend to exhibit similar failures at similar times (i.e. the brakes on an automobile). The true perception of a machine will never be complete until we add chaos to our AI systems and allow proper evaluation of information obtained. Sensory equipment in conjunction with the UUT provide a platform for compound errors or erroneous information to be gathered. AI routines should monitor sensor data for proper/improper functioning and base conclusions accordingly.

Predictive Sensitivity offers a strategy for weighing alternative testing strategies, giving the operator a quantitative rating of which strategy can provide the most information to facilitate the circuit card diagnosis. Using the Predictive Sensitivity information, the technician can be guided to other tests to verify if a specific component fault exists, it also guides the technician to determine other possible non-related defective components.

The authors are not attempting to control the science for this discipline but rather to promote the extension of machine intelligence to its unlimited potential. There are preadonnas in society that can actually inhibit the natural evolution of a science by attempting to control a discipline with their own peculiar ideas. The present understanding of the Universe must not stop or close our minds to what we uncover as we progress in our understanding of various sciences. Let's hope that mankind, in general, will continue relentlessly to obtain an understanding of our environment and use the techniques & tools which work best.

REFERENCES

- [1] Marvin Minsky, *The Society of Mind*, 1988. Simon & Schuser, NY.
- [2] Christopher G. Langton, Charles Taylor, J. Doyne Farmer & Steen Rasmussen, *Artificial Life, II*, 1992. Sante Fe Institute.
- [3] Larry V. Kirkland & Dr. Lloyd G. Allred, "Adaptive Machine-Based Intelligence for Sensor-Based Systems", 1992. SimTec Conference, NASA Space Center.
- [4] Daniel S. Weld/Johan de Kleer, *Qualitive Reasoning About Physical Systems*, 1990. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, Inc., San Mateo, CA.